

or physical exertion DID is often conditional. The primary treatment for dissociative identity disorder is long-term psychotherapy with the aim of deconstructing different personalities and integrating them into a single person. Other treatments include cognitive and creative therapy . While there are no medications that clearly treat this illness , antidepressants, anti-anxiety pills or tranquilizers can be used to help reduce the psychological symptoms associated with it. With appropriate treatment , Many people who suffer from DID experience improvements in their ability to function in their work and private lives. In 1988, Dell¹ conducted a survey of clinicians to assess the reactions they saw from others because of their interest in dissociative identity disorder (DID), previously called multiple personality disorder. More than eighty percent of the 62 participants who treated patients with DID say they had "moderate to extreme" reactions from their colleagues. These responses included attempts by their patients to refuse hospitalization or to force their patients to be discharged, even patients who responders felt were at serious risk of committing suicide. Dell hypothesized that the emotional responses to the diagnosis of IPD were the result of the anxiety brought on by the "strange, disturbing clinical presentation"¹ of the disorder, comparable to the emotional responses of some clinicians to psychiatric emergency patients.

Keywords: *DID, Dissociative Identity Disorder, DID, Stress, Psychological Disorders*

1. Introduction

Another factor contributing to the heated debate surrounding the diagnosis of DID is disagreement over the importance of observed symptoms :

- a. *dissociative identity disorder a condition with a distinct and subtle collection of core symptoms and behaviors whose presence some clinicians fail?*
- b. *patient is right in front of them?*
- c. *Or is it deliberate malingering and/or iatrogenically induced symptoms produced by other professionals who believe that something is not there?*

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A third and especially important reason for the controversy is the fear that offenders will be "escaped" from punishment by a pure justice system that attributes the behavior to another personality and does not hold the perpetrator accountable.

The diagnosis of DID is controversial. The cases of DID report by Frankel , Ganaway , and McHugh have instead been attributed to social contagion, hypnotic suggestion, and misdiagnosis. ("Dissociative Identity Disorder - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)") These authors claimed that people diagnosed with dissociative identity disorder are highly hypnotizable and, as a result, incredibly open to suggestions. They argue that these individuals are likely to follow direct or implicit hypnotic suggestions, and that the majority of IPD diagnoses are made by a few professional psychiatrists. ("Dissociative Identity Disorder - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)") "Borderline Personality Disorder In 1993 , Lauer , Black, and Keen¹² concluded that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is an epiphenomenon of borderline personality disorder . They came to this conclusion after discovering slight difference in the symptoms that distinguish the two diagnoses . Instead, those with disturbed personalities They described what they called a "syndrome" of symptoms that can be found in people, particularly borderline personality disorder .

DID does not have a clear clinical picture, laboratory tests are unreliable, cannot be successfully differentiated from other diseases, does not have a clear natural history, and does not have a familial pattern. In the same year, despite tries by young people to address this issue by empirically evaluating the literature , North et al.¹³ concluded that the diagnosis was not "really" confirmed, but that they were "starting to believe in its existence" nonetheless. "The available information currently does not sufficiently justify the validity of DID as a separate diagnosis," they said, but this also does not disprove the concept. Later, Spira edited a book by those who advocate the existence of DID, describing treatment options .

Researchers Loewenstein¹⁶ and Bliss¹⁷ found that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is present and spontaneous autohypnotic concluded that the symptoms are essential for the phenomenology of DID. Gelinas described autohypnotic and post - traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms in patients with dissociative identity disorder (DID) . These symptoms were likely a reaction to childhood sexual abuse. Spiegel and Rosenfeld¹⁹ attributed the "age regression" (to another

younger person) showed in ICD patients to early trauma and argued that trauma-related PTSD symptoms are important for ICD. Horevitz and Braun found that 70 percent of patients diagnosed with "multiple personality disorder (DPD)" would equally fit the criteria for borderline personality disorder, according to their registry review. They concluded that dissociative identity disorder was a separate entity but was overdiagnosed as they found other patients who could not be characterized as such. Coons et al. conducted assessments with the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM Disorders (SCID) and the Structured Interview for DSM-III-R Personality Disorders (SIDP-R), the Dissociative Disorder Interview Program (DDIS), Beck Depression, Beck Hopelessness, and Dissociative.

2. Scale of Experiences in Patients Diagnosed with DID (DES) and Shipley Institute of Living scales

found that 64 percent of patients diagnosed with DID meet the criteria for borderline personality disorder but met most of the criteria for borderline personality disorder, even among those who did not meet all criteria for borderline personality disorder. However, as found by Horevitz and Braun, one-third of people previously diagnosed with Axis I DID based on the assessment scales did not meet the criteria for any Axis II disorder. A special note is that DES is higher in subjects with DID than in other subjects. Coons et al., DID is a "syndrome" that occurs in people with disturbed personalities, particularly borderline personality disorder, where both borderline personality disorder and DID are on the same character disorder spectrum and represent the more severe end of DID. They concluded. They argued that DID is caused by a substrate of borderline features. The authors argued that the plethora of ICD-related symptoms support their view, including insomnia, sexual dysfunction, anger, suicide, self-harm, drug and alcohol abuse, anxiety, paranoia, somatization, dissociation, mood changes, and pathological changes in relationships. Herman suggested that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is an extreme stress disorder and may be a form of complex post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) because of prolonged and repetitive trauma.

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Watkins and Watkins make it clear that there is a difference between ego states and alters, although some people refer to the changes found in DID as ego states. In their understanding, the ego state is "an orderly system of action and experience, the parts of which are connected by a common principle but separated from other such states by barriers that are more or less permeable." The alters in DID "have their own identity that includes a center of initiative and experience; they have a characteristic self-representation that may differ from how the patient is generally viewed or perceived; they have their own autobiographical memory and distinguish what they distinguish.

It is necessary to understand that they have their own actions and experiences from those made and experienced by other ego states." This is how Watkins , Watkins , et al. separate the concept of alter from ego states. Exposure to extreme indecision and abusive situations in early childhood must be overcome through elaborate denial so that the child can overcome the event. The effects of believing it's happening to someone else are often attributed to the development of dissociative identity disorder. The " solution" to a major trauma in a child at that time in life may be a dissociated identity. This is due to the life stage a child is in where imaginary friends "exist".

symptoms are more likely to manifest themselves when the traumatic event occurs later in childhood or later in adult life . Violent child maltreatment, a chaotic and disoriented attachment style, as well as a lack of social and family support appear to precede the development of dissociative identity disorder (DID). The tendency to separate appears to be due to a pathogenic family structure and an attachment problem bought early in the child's life. This appears to be the case regardless of the individual's initial temperament or genetics. The authoritarian and rigid parenting approach often adopted by these patients was ironically accompanied by a reversal of the traditional parent-child dynamic. Blizard hypothesized that children displaying a disorganized or disoriented attachment pattern may be isolating conflicting representations of parental behavior and that different attachment patterns may be implicated in various personalities in IPD . Blizard also hypothesized that these children may be parsing their representations of conflicting parental behavior. The chaos illustrated in the attachment model of an DID patient is particularly noteworthy considering some of the more recent discoveries in neuroscience about this condition. For more recent research on dissociative identity disorder in neuroscience, considerations of attention and memory should be considered.

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This variability was attributed to subtle neuropsychological deficits in the memory/distraction factor like that seen in attention deficit disorder (ADD). In another study, patients with DID show a prepulse inhibition (PPI) in the acoustic startle reflex. This suggests that DID patients have maladaptive attentional processes when functioning at a controlled level, but not when functioning at a pre-attentive automatic level. Patients with other dissociative disorders did not show this PPI. Patients with DID have an elevated level of alertness, resulting in decreased habituation of startle reflexes and an increase in PPI.

This response is an intentional process that diverts attention from stimuli perceived as unpleasant or potentially dangerous. The authors concluded that an abnormal pattern of voluntary attention processes may therefore be a hallmark of DID .

A third study found that patients with DID have decreased regional cerebral blood flow (rCBF) bilaterally (like that seen in attention deficit disorder) in regions of the orbitofrontal cortex and increased rCBF as well as increased rCBF in the median and superior frontal regions .

3. Memory

It was found that the degree of clear fragmentation of learned items depended on the degree to which information was interpreted and kept in ways that had a unique meaning to the change or "personality state." A diagnosis of ICD was made by Nissen et al. This was discovered in a memory study of subjects diagnosed with DID. They concluded that "implicit" memories can be most effectively stored and retrieved during different states of behavioral awareness, and this is the first time they occur. On the other hand, one identity was able to detect neutral expressions bought by the other identity. In addition, memories of seemingly neutral expressions transmitted by auditory input but visually recovered showed inter-identity memory transfer. This was the case when the memory was recalled visually. Huntjens et al. Clinical models of amnesia in ICD should not have deficiencies for emotionally neutral content. One study, which did not exclude patients suffering from PTSD , found that patients with DID have 19.2 percent smaller hippocampal volume and 31.6 percent smaller amygdala volume compared to healthy participants . symptoms . In another

study, trauma-exposed subjects with PTSD symptoms but no DID have significantly reduced amygdala and hippocampus and significantly impaired cognition, compared with controls. This contrasted with trauma-exposed patients with DID symptoms but no PTSD, who had normal cognition with normal amygdala and hippocampi in the same study. Further studies are needed to decide whether the symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID) play a neurologically protective, defensive role by creating a neuroprotective environment that improves the neurotoxic consequences of traumatic stress.

4. Sexual Abuse Is More Common Than Physical Abuse

Stankiewicz and Golczynska, this is expected to be the case. Examination of the patient's medical history will usually show the onset of dissociative symptoms between 5 and 10 years of age, and changes occurring around 6 years of age. By the time they become adults (adolescents report about 24), however, most of these will disappear quickly once treatment is started. Childhood abuse is often reported, with sexual abuse being more common than physical abuse in most cases. The frequency of sexual abuse is higher than the frequency of physical abuse. Patients diagnosed with DID often express persistent suicidal feelings, with an increased risk of trying suicide. Even when promiscuous intercourse is common, patients often report having a lower libido and unable to reach orgasm.

Some patients reported finding themselves as the other sex or wearing clothing associated with the other sex. Some said they were the other sex. Patients often report having "extrasensory experiences" associated with dissociative symptoms, also known as hallucinations in certain contexts. They describe hearing voices, going through phases of forgetfulness, going through phases of depersonalization, and may refer to themselves in the plural ("we" instead of "me") when talking about themselves. These patients have a highly irregular work history, as they suffer from such an elevated level of dissociation in addition to many somatic symptoms (some cases like Briquet's syndrome or somatization disorder).

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Patients often experience periods that they cannot account for, they may meet people who know them but do not know them, and they may discover things they own, do not remember buying, and would not normally wear.

therapy for ICD do so because they are experiencing emotional, psychotic-like, or somatic symptoms. However, in an emergency setting with a new patient who does not know his name, it is important to consider that the patient may have a true psychosis. This is because the majority of "Jane Does " and "John Does " found in psychiatric emergency settings turned out to be psychotic rather than a dissociative state or had an associated functional or organic psychosis. Although ICD patients often report hearing sounds, North et al discovered that the hallucinations reported in IPD often show a sophisticated visual character. This was shown to be the case in DID .

5. Patients Diagnosed with DID

Patients diagnosed with DID often show an acute sensitivity to interpersonal trust and concerns of rejection, making it difficult to supply short-term therapy in a third party-managed setting. Patients with dissociative identity disorder are seen by therapists as weekly or fortnightly outpatients for several years to fuse their personality states while keeping the full spectrum of experience involved in all alters. When patients feel a danger to their psychosocial health, they often experience changes in their personality state. Through this exchange, an alter who feels overwhelmed can take a break, while another alters who is better equipped to manage the situation appears. The DID patient's experience with the relationships and conditions prevailing in the family of origin can be replicated by the alter system. As seen by Kluft , alternative identities or personality states are key components of dissociative identity disorder (DID). Kluft does not see changes as obstacles, diversions, or objects that need to be suppressed or circumvented in any way. In fact, he claims that if the therapist does not engage with these various incarnations of the client's personality, he does not discover any evidence of progress. It is widespread practice to recommend a cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) approach that involves helping the patient find more adaptive coping strategies rather than "changing" them when distressed . This approach also includes effective communication with alters. This can be improved by teaching the patient relaxation exercises,

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suggesting they take a few minutes off from the environment, and helping the patient control their cognitive distortions, both in themselves and in the world. The therapist will strive to serve as an example of healthy connection as well as proper, calm and thoughtful responses to challenging situations.

Kluft , there is no need to be overly concerned if the patient experiences multiple personality states , as major alter systems typically collapse as treatment progresses. While one may at times fall into the trap of assuming that the host personality is the patient's identity, familiarity with prominent personality states is essential, although this is not the case.

One of the most important things to address during treatment is the anxiety that a person with an externalizing or antisocial personality condition will be destroyed by therapy . This anxiety stems from the belief that the psychiatrist's goal is to "get rid of" a " variable" who may have engaged in illegal or even violent behavior in the past . This is not a suitable target to work with during treatment. The personality state, developed to protect the self from harm and abuse, has the potential to become a powerful and vital part when integrated more harmoniously into the overall personality structure. A rare type of mental illness known as dissociative identity disorder (also abbreviated as DID) affects about 1.5% of the world's population. This condition is often misdiagnosed and often requires multiple evaluations to reach a definitive diagnosis. Patients often present with self-harming behaviors , including suicide attempts . This exercise discusses the diagnosis and treatment of dissociative identity disorder, as well as the role played by an interprofessional team in the care of patients diagnosed with dissociative identity disorder (DID). This exercise includes a discussion on the link between dissociative identity disorder and suicidal behavior.

Behavioral symptoms are a key part in reaching a diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder. The rare dissociative identity disorder (also called DID) is characterized by severe behavioral and mental health symptoms . Before 1994, this condition was called Multiple Personality Disorder.

A dissociative identity disorder has been found in approximately 1.5% of the total population worldwide. Patients with this diagnosis often come to the emergency room with a variety of symptoms , including self-harming behavior and even drug use . It is important to note that DID

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has been seen and described in several countries. It has also been associated with phrases such as "being possessed by demons" and "having the outside world". Although these terms were used to describe more than one case report, it was not until much later that trauma and its connotations became associated with DID.

6. etiology

In most cases, dissociative identity disorder is caused by significant childhood emotional trauma and/or physical violence. The old model of imagination, often associated with suggestibility, cognitive distortions, and fantasy, was rejected in favor of the model developed by Dalenberg and colleagues that detailed the role trauma plays in development. from dissociative disorder. However, more recent research tends to depict a mix of both some effects of severe trauma (which can be of any form , including physical, emotional, or sexual) and cognitive suggestions. This is because extreme trauma can take any form. It has been found that the stress experienced by the individual as a direct result of a traumatic event contributes to the formation of a correct understanding that the traumatic event is not real. This means leaving one's body, etc. and even post- traumatic dissociation, which includes things like poor sleep . On the other hand, according to the fantasy hypothesis, those with elevated levels of sensitivity, susceptibility to psychiatric symptoms, media exposure, and potential social isolation and vulnerability were more likely to read fantasy.

Altogether the concept of DID has been studied by several well-known psychologists, including Kluff , among others. This theory explains the predisposing factors for dissociation. These factors include the ability to dissociate, overwhelming traumatic experiences that distort reality, the creation of alters with specific names and identities, and a lack of external stability that causes the child to engage in self-soothing behaviors to endure these stressors . For DID to develop, these four conditions must first be present.

7. epidemiology

There is an incidence of dissociative disorders of between one and five percent in the general population worldwide . One to one-half percent of people in this population have severe dissociative identity disorder. Before a patient is diagnosed with dissociative identity disorder, the patient may receive treatment for anywhere from five to 12.5 years. Patients with dissociative identity disorder tend to have higher rates of both non-suicidal and suicidal self-harming behavior.

8. pathophysiology

According to the International Association for the Study of Trauma and Dissociation, a DID person is someone who experiences separate identities that function independently and are autonomous from each other. This disclosure is provided by the International Association for the Study of Trauma and Dissociation. Alternative identities, also known as alters, are independent identities that can show unique behaviors, have different memories from other people, and even use their own unique language and expressions. This is how the International Society defines alternative identities. Behaviors such as trance, changes in posture, blinking and rolling eyes are indications that a person's level of consciousness has changed. Putnam and colleagues' primary hypothesis are that "alternative identities result from the inability of many traumatized children to develop a unified sense of self that is sustained in a variety of behavioral situations . " This is especially true if the first traumatic exposure occurred in children before the age of five. In the 1990s, groups serving in inpatient services conducted research on various theories. The best way to diagnose both Historical and Physical Dissociative identity disorder is for experienced psychologists as well as psychiatrists to take a comprehensive medical history of the patient.

Because parts of dissociation and even amnesia are commonly present in people with dissociative identity disorder (DID), these individuals are often misdiagnosed with other personality disorders, particularly borderline personality disorder. When conducting diagnostic evaluations, it is sometimes necessary to conduct longitudinal evaluations and take comprehensive medical histories. When it comes to history, information is usually compiled from a variety of sources. Nervous system examinations such as electroencephalograms , lumbar punctures, and brain imaging are often necessary to rule out the possibility of autoimmune encephalitis . Classically,

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dissociative disorders are understood to be characterized by normally occurring disturbances of consciousness, memory, identity, and behavior. Positive symptoms are often associated with "new personalities, derealization , " and negative symptoms include things like autism and stroke. Disorders are conventionally divided into "positive" and "negative" symptoms . Positive symptoms include things like "new personalities, derealization ."

9. Although Part of the Broader Spectrum of Dissociative Disorders

Although Dissociative Identity Disorder is part of the broader spectrum of dissociative disorders, it has more precise criteria , these are described in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition . At least two or more different personalities are needed to meet the criteria for DID, as outlined in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual, version 5 . Behavior, sense of awareness, memory and feeling of the external environment are distinctive characteristics of each personality. Amnesia, or marked gaps in memory and memories of ordinary and traumatic experiences, is a symptom that affects people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) . They are not allowed to be related to the use of substances or to be part of cultural norms or practices. It is important that these symptoms lead to a significant reduction in the person's ability to function in daily life.

10. Evaluation

As just discussed, it is extremely important to obtain a comprehensive history from various sources as well as many longitudinal assessments over time. However, several diagnostic techniques for DID have been developed over the years. Listed below are some of these: The Dissociative Experiences Scale is a 28-item self-report tool that largely explores amnesia, depersonalization, derealization , depersonalization, and information absorption from the outside world.

11. Dissociation Questionnaire

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The Emotion Regulation Difficulties Scale (COURS) consists of 36 subjective items related to, among other topics, goal-directed difficulties at work, impulsivity, emotional reactions to events, and the capacity to self-regulate emotions. Treatment/Management Core constructs from studies with personality disorders can be incorporated into some treatment techniques for dissociative identity disorder as a three-pronged approach :

- *Creating a safe environment, keeping stability and reducing symptoms.*
- *Confronting, processing, and integrating traumatic experiences into daily life Integration of one's identity and therapeutic healing*

The first step is to ensure that patients with dissociative identity disorder are safe, as a considerable proportion of these patients show suicidal ideation and self-esteem. It is essential to take precautions against this risk. The second phase of treatment focuses on working with traumatic memories, which includes tolerating, processing and integrating the effects of past trauma . This can focus on continuing to re-access traumatic memories while assuming various alternative identities and can also aid the process of sharing memories. The third and final stage of treatment is when the primary emphasis is placed on the patient's relationship to both himself and the rest of the world. Trust and a solid therapeutic alliance are fostered and encouraged throughout the entire treatment process. The most common method is called psychodynamic psychotherapy and includes a series of steps outlined above. Recent modalities include the practice of trauma -focused cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and dialectical behavioral therapy (DBT).

No randomized controlled studies have been conducted on CBT. The use of DBT skills is often the result of borderline personality disorder and dissociative identity disorder sharing some common symptoms. While there are many different approaches to therapy, some key aspects of treatment include increased education, emotional regulation, learning to manage stressors, and improving daily functioning. Hypnosis as a form of therapy is another form of care that can be used. According to current research, patients suffering from DID are more prone to hypnosis than patients suffering from other clinical populations . Some research as recently as 2009 has shown that hypnosis can be an effective treatment for dissociative identity disorder (DID). Many people with dissociative identity disorder are autohypnotic . One intervention that can help promote the

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development of identities important to the therapeutic process is to access backup identities not present in the session. This is one of the strategies that can be used. Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing is another method used to treat this condition (EMDR).

Still, recommendations recommend using EMDR as part of integrative therapy . EMDR processing is only recommended when the patient is generally stable and has good coping skills. EMDR interventions are important to reduce and control symptoms, strengthen the ego, negotiate consent with alternative identities and where proper, and prepare alternative identities.

12. Use of psychopharmacology

It is not considered a first-line treatment for DID. It is possible to take medication to treat some reported symptoms . Mood disorder and post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) drugs are among the most used drugs (post-traumatic stress disorder). The use of psychopharmacological drugs continues to present challenges since different alters may report a variety of symptoms and some alters may report adherence to treatment while others may not. A review of the relevant literature revealed that many drugs have been tried in the treatment of IPD, including antipsychotic drugs, mood stabilizers, and even stimulants ; however, no drug has been shown to be successful in the treatment of DID.

13. Differential diagnosis

As mentioned earlier, the most common differential diagnoses include borderline personality disorder, histrionic personality disorder, and even primary psychotic disorders such as schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorders. This is because these conditions are often misdiagnosed as something else entirely. As mentioned earlier, patients suffering from dissociative identity disorder often show symptoms such as amnesia and dissociation, which are also seen in patients with borderline personality disorder. Patients ' symptoms are often misdiagnosed as hallucinations, or both are considered symptoms of psychosis, often leading to the prescription of antipsychotic drugs. Symptoms of psychosis include Given the emphasis on traumatic experiences;

a differential diagnosis of post-traumatic stress disorder can also be made . borderline The differential diagnosis of personality disorder is the most common diagnosis. Borderline personality disorder is often associated with significant trauma , typically manifested by micropsychotic and dissociative symptoms . Related Studies and Ongoing Trials In the 1990s and early 2000s, there was many previously reported case studies and case reports. Naturalistic and longitudinal studies currently in use to influence therapy outcomes have detailed several added therapeutic strategies.

14. Prognosis

Dissociative identity disorder is, unfortunately, a medical illness that is often found later in life. Often, people are misdiagnosed with various conditions as noted above and are treated with medications or even therapies that do not directly address DID . Once treatment has begun, it is typical for this to continue for the rest of the patient's life, as DID patients continue to require fact-based and reality-based treatments. Planning the safety of patients throughout their lives is essential. If treatment and proper diagnosis are not provided, the prognosis is not good. Complications Due to the presence of both alters and latent trauma , patients continue to be at elevated risk of engaging in behaviors that could result in self-harm.

More recent research studies have found suicidal ideation, particularly during dissociation, characterized by reduced pain tolerance and increased emotional dysregulation. These findings have been presented in several publications. Before delving into more complex forms of psychotherapy, most therapeutic modalities encourage patients to do safety planning and reality check first. Inpatient hospitalizations and day treatment programs may also be recommended for patients struggling with thoughts of self-harming behavior, poor impulse control, or acute mood dysregulation. This is because these patients often struggle with these three problems at the same time. Medication can be added for mood stabilization .

15. Patient Protection and Education

Once a diagnosis is made, the primary goal of patient education should be to educate patients on the correct diagnosis. It is highly recommended that family members receive education about the nature of this disease, which should include safety and grounding techniques as well as the presence of alters. Another key part is continuing to develop a strong therapeutic alliance with the treatment team and actively taking part in the maintenance of safety procedures. Training can be done with multiple alters not communicating with each other and this needs to be recognized. On the other hand, patients with IPD often do not want their diagnosis to be made public and their right to privacy must be respected.

16. Conclusion

An interprofessional healthcare team is needed to treat dissociative identity disorder. This team will typically include medical professionals such as psychiatrists, intermediate practitioners, nursing staff, specialist therapists, trauma counselors, peer counselors, and therapists who communicate and collaborate with one another throughout the treatment process. The team is completed by a psychiatrist and a general care doctor. Maintaining a strong therapeutic alliance with both the patient and related family members stays extremely important. DID patients need frequent check-ups and follow-up appointments and focus almost daily on safety planning and fact-based interventions.

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